

CONSIDERING STUDENTS' INTERESTS TO PERSONALIZE LEARNING IN THE CLASSROOM

Antonio Membrive^{1*}, María Isabel Vizquerra²

¹Dr., University of Girona, SPAIN, antonio.membrive@udg.edu

² Ms., University of Barcelona, SPAIN, mariaisabelvizquerra@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract

In recent years, a widespread loss of interest among students towards school content and tasks has been detected, which can translate into lack of engagement and, in extreme cases, school dropout. Many students perceive school as something distant from what they consider relevant to their life projects and interests. Faced with this situation, several authors and education professionals have pointed out the need to incorporate student voice into school practices (Mitra, 2018). This idea encompasses educational practices in which students are allowed to share their perspective and make decisions about the teaching and learning process. In our view, one of the most prominent pedagogical proposals among those seeking to incorporate student voice is personalized learning (Bray & McClaskey, 2015; Coll, 2018).

According to Coll (2018), personalized learning involves a set of strategies aimed at promoting students' sense-making of school learning and attributing personal value to it. Sense-making and personal value attribution occur when teaching and learning practices help learners to better understand themselves and the world around them, enabling them to participate in it by connecting with aspects of their past and personal history, their daily lives, and their projected future personal projects. Based on the literature in the field, there are several ways in which teachers can contribute to students' sense-making of learning, and thereby promote their engagement and active participation in teaching and learning activities. Some of these include: a) promoting connections between students' learning experiences inside and outside of school, b) allowing students to make decisions about different aspects of teaching-learning activities, c) encouraging student reflection on their own learning process and their identity as learners, or d) incorporating students' learning goals and interests into educational practices (Ramos & Engel, 2023).

In this study, we focus on this latter strategy, which involves designing activities that allow students to link learning content to relevant goals and enhance their potential to become objects of interest (Solari et al., 2022). Traditionally, there has been a tendency to conceptualize interest as an intrapsychological, stable, and innate phenomenon, whereby a person has preferences for a particular activity or learning topic. This tendency has often led to the implementation of teaching strategies based on asking students about the content they find most interesting and proposing activities related to these topics. However, from a sociocultural perspective of personalized learning, interests are considered a dynamic and interpsychological process that can be transformed with the help of others (Renninger & Hidi, 2019). From this approach, teaching strategies aiming to incorporate students' learning interests should enable learners to identify, question, value, and reflect on their current interests, as well as generate new interests and establish new goals to guide their learning.

Although there have been some empirical studies dedicated to exploring this strategy, research into how the incorporation of students' interests can be realized through specific actions in the classroom is still largely unexplored. Therefore, in this study, we aim to identify the educational support that teachers offer to incorporate and/or develop students' interests and describe in depth the type of activities that are implemented, their objectives regarding interest transformation, and their link to the curricular content.

For this purpose, as part of a research project called by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and funded by the State Research Agency of Spanish government (Reference: PID2020-116223RB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033), we selected an educational practice from a public school in Spain that

explicitly mentions taking into consideration students' interests in order to personalize learning. The practice is called 'Interesting Projects' and aims for students to learn curriculum content by participating in projects where they can make several decisions based on their interests. We conducted a non-participant observation in the classroom, where we recorded class sessions on video and audio, wrote narrative records, and took field notes. We also collected documents outlining the practice's design and the materials used by teachers in the classroom. Finally, we conducted interviews with teachers and students to better understand the development of the projects.

Through the analysis of the collected data, we have identified specific actions in which the incorporation of students' interests materializes. The results show that teachers employ at least five types of sub-strategies that are implemented sequentially and help students be more interested and engaged in the classroom. These strategies are: 1) Spark interests, through exposure to diverse and stimulating activities such as field trips or expert visits, 2) Explore interests, with guided questions aimed at probing students' anecdotes and experiences related to a specific topic, 3) Center interests, using tools and guides that help to concretize learning interests and to compare them with those of the whole class, 4) Deepen interests, by defining tasks with students help and by offering sources of information that are diverse in content and format, and 5) Evaluate interests, generating moments for evaluation and reflection on the satisfaction of interests through teaching and learning activities. Thus, this empirical study offers important insights into the multifaceted process of incorporating student interests into teaching practices, ultimately proposing a range of sub-strategies to enrich personalized learning experiences in educational settings.

Keywords: students' interests, teaching strategies, personalized learning

REFERENCE LIST

- Bray, B., & McClaskey, K. (2015). *Make Learning Personal: The What, Who, Wow, Where, and Why*. Corwin.
- Coll, C. (2018). *La personalización del aprendizaje escolar*. Graó.
- Mitra, D. L. (2018). Student voice in secondary schools: The possibility for deeper change. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 56(5), 473–487. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-01-2018-0007>.
- Ramos, M. W., & Engel, A. (2023). *Experiências inovadoras na escola básica: relatos Espanha e Brasil*. Editora CRV.
- Renninger, K. A., & Hidi, S. E. (2019). Interest development and learning. In K. A. Renninger & S. E. Hidi (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of motivation and learning* (pp. 265–290). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316823279.013>
- Solari, M., Vizquerra, M.I., & Engel, A. (2023). Students' interests for personalized learning: An analysis guide. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 38, 1073–1109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-022-00656-3>